

FABRICATION AND PROPERTIES OF HOT ISOSTATIC PRESSED STAINLESS STEEL MATRIX COMPOSITE COMPOUNDS

Antero Jokinen & Simo-Pekka Hannula
VTT Manufacturing Technology
P.O.Box 1703, 02044 VTT
Espoo, Finland

ABSTRACT

In this work the manufacturing and properties of stainless steel matrix composite compounds are studied. The compounds were fabricated by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) using mixed austenitic stainless steel and TiN powders for the composite and duplex or austenitic stainless steels for the substrate of the compound. The properties and bonding of the compounds were investigated by tensile and fracture toughness testing and microstructures and fracture surfaces were analysed. Special attention was paid to the effects of reinforcement content and substrate alloy on the properties.

The results show that manufacturing of full dense TiN particulate reinforced stainless steel matrix composite compounds can successfully be carried out by HIP techniques. In the mechanical testing the specimens fractured near the interface but clearly through the composite and not at the compound interface. The strength of the interface between the bonded materials is at least equal to that of the composite alloy and the bonding between the materials is sufficient for manufacturing of the compound structures. The fracture propagates through the TiN particulates indicating that the bonding between the reinforcement and the matrix alloy is good, but the TiN particulates are brittle.

INTRODUCTION

The addition of ceramic particulates into steels is an effective way of increasing their wear resistance [1-3]. If properly designed, it is possible to combine the good corrosion resistance of stainless steels and the excellent wear resistance of ceramics. These properties are needed in many machine parts used in the process industries. However, the ductility of the composites is typically very low and the manufactured parts are quite brittle limiting the use of these materials in components. Therefore, it is often desirable to manufacture only selected surfaces of components out of these materials.

Powder metallurgy (PM) is the most practical way to produce stainless steel matrix composites. With specific mixing techniques the ceramic particulates can be homogeneously added to steel powder [4]. By hot isostatic pressing (HIP) it is possible to manufacture composite compounds through consolidation of powders to solid parts. In addition, the products can be fabricated to near net shape in order to minimize machining of the hard composite materials.

In this work the manufacturing and properties of some selected stainless steel matrix composite compounds are studied. Results relating to the mechanical properties of these compounds as well as microstructural investigations including analysis of the fracture surfaces of the fractured samples are presented and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To combine PM based stainless steels with a PM based stainless steel matrix composite specially designed test samples were used. One half of the sample consisted of stainless steel and the other half of a stainless steel composite.

POWDERS

Austenitic stainless steel powders of types AISI 316 (UNS 31600) and 7Mo (7MoSS) and duplex stainless steel powder of type Duplex 2205 (UNS 31800) were used for the substrate materials of the compound structures. The matrix alloy for the composite coatings was an austenitic stainless steel powder 7MoSS and the reinforcements were Titanium Nitride (TiN) particulates. The particle size of the powders is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Particle size of the powders used in the experiments.

	AISI 316 Substrate	Duplex 2205 Substrate	7MoSS Substrate	7MoSS MMC	TiN MMC
Particle size (μm)	45-250	-200	-250	-100	45-125

MANUFACTURE OF THE SAMPLES

The capsule design for the manufacturing of the samples is presented in Fig. 1. Low carbon steel capsules with dimensions of $\phi 12 \times 230$ mm and $10 \times 30 \times 80$ mm were used. The capsule was filled in the upright position. First the bottom of the capsule was filled approximately half way with the substrate powder. Then a plate corresponding to the substrate alloy was placed on the top of the substrate powder. The intermediate plate thickness was 0.5 mm for AISI 316, 1.45 mm for Duplex 2205 and 0.62 mm for 7MoSS steels.

Figure 1. The capsule design used in the experiments.

The 7MoSS and Titanium Nitride powder (12 or 30 vol.%) were wet-mixed with 4 weight % ethanol in a Turbula shaking mixer for 30 minutes. After mixing, the wet composite powder was filled on the top of the capsule and the ethanol was removed by annealing the capsule for three hours at the temperature of 90°C. The vacuum degassing of the powders was carried out by connecting the capsule to a turbomolecular vacuum pump and heating it slowly up to 520°C, where it was held for three hours before sealing the evacuation tube.

The samples were HIPed for three hours at the temperature of 1180°C and the pressure of 100 MPa. After HIPing the samples were annealed for one hour at 1180°C and water quenched. For comparison, some samples consisting of only 7MoSS, 7MoSS-12vol.%TiN or 7MoSS-30vol.%TiN were also manufactured.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Mechanical testing included tensile and impact testing at room temperature. Specimens were machined from the HIPed samples so that the interface between the bonded materials was in the middle of the specimen. Tensile test samples had dimensions of either $\phi 5 \times 25$ mm, $\phi 6 \times 30$ mm or $\phi 7 \times 35$ mm with wedged ends and the unnotched impact test specimens were machined to dimensions of $5 \times 10 \times 55$ mm. Tensile testing was carried out according to the EN 10 002-1 standard and the impact testing was performed according to the EN 10 045-1 standard. In some tensile specimens the approximate elongation of the composite part (A_{mmc}) was measured separately.

METALLOGRAPHY

The microstructure of the compounds and especially the interface between the bonded materials were investigated with an optical (OM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM). The characterization of the fracture surfaces was carried out both in transverse and longitudinal directions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiments showed that the manufacturing of stainless steel composite compounds can successfully be carried out by using HIP techniques. All of the manufactured samples and materials were found to consolidate to full density and the TiN particulates were generally homogeneously distributed in the stainless steel matrix. However, in 7MoSS-30vol.%TiN compounds TiN was occasionally found to agglomerate next to the interface of the substrate alloy pointing out the necessity of careful handling of samples in the preparation stage. The intermediate plate between the materials prevented mixing of the powders and all the materials seemed to be strongly bonded to each other. No reaction layers neither cracks could be detected by optical microscopy at the interface (e.g., Fig. 2).

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The results of the mechanical tests on the compound samples and the reference materials are summarized in Table 2. The addition of the TiN particulates decreased both the strength and the elongation of the 7MoSS steel. Especially, the tensile strength (R_m), elongation (A_5) and impact ductility were reduced dramatically, but also the proof strength of the 7MoSS steel was reduced.

The proof strength of the AISI 316/7MoSS-TiN compounds was very low because yielding started of the AISI 316 substrate. During the elongation the AISI 316 work hardened until the stress exceeded the yield strength of the composite. After that both of the materials elongated until the specimen fractured of the composite. The fracture occurred typically near, but not at the interface in the composite part of the specimen. In the AISI 316/7MoSS-12vol.%TiN

compound the elongation of the AISI 316 was from 11 to 23% and the elongation of the composite from 4 to 12%. The AISI 316/7MoSS-30vol.%TiN compound fractured before any marked elongation of the composite.

In the Duplex 2205/7MoSS-12vol.%TiN compound the yielding started from the composite and it work hardened until the yield strength of the Duplex 2205 was achieved. Both of the materials elongated until the specimen fractured of the composite. The elongation was about 0.4-6% for the substrate and 2-16% for the composite. The Duplex 2205/7MoSS-30vol.%TiN compounds fractured of the composite before the yield strength was achieved.

The 7MoSS/7MoSS-TiN compounds elongated only of the composite and the yield strength of the substrate was not achieved.

The average tensile strength of the compound specimens is depicted in Fig. 3. In the compound structures the strength of composites varies a lot and the tensile strength of composites is in all compounds lower than that of the bulk composite material. Since also the elongation of composites in compound structures is smaller than that of bulk composites the interface may slightly deteriorate the properties of these compounds at least in uniaxial tension. Since cracking occurred near the interface the reduction in properties may be a consequence of internal stresses caused by the differences in thermal coefficients of expansion between the substrates and the composites during temperature cycling in manufacturing.

The average impact toughness values (C) of the compound structures and the bulk composite materials are presented in Fig. 4. The monolithic 7MoSS did not fracture in the impact test. As expected, the addition of TiN particulates decreased considerably the impact energy of the 7MoSS steel leading to the fracture of the specimen at a very low impact energy. In the case of 12 vol.% TiN composite compound structures the energy absorbed during fracture is larger than that of the bulk composite material. This is probably due to the tough substrate material which obviously absorbs some of the energy during the fracture. In the case of 30 vol.%TiN composite compound structures the absorbed energy was the same as that of the reference composite material. All of the compound structures fractured through the composite close to the interface of the bonded materials.

Figure 2. The microstructure of the Duplex 2205/7MoSS-12 vol.%TiN composite compound. The arrow indicates the interface between the intermediate plate and the substrate.

Table 2. Results of the mechanical testing.

Specimen	R _p 0.2 (MPa)	R _m (MPa)	A5 (%)	A _{mmc} (%)	C (J/cm ²)
7MoSS	516	950	51		> 600
	512	947	50.5		> 600
7MoSS - 12 % TiN	448	586	14.8	15	28
	428	577	14.0	14	32
7MoSS - 30 % TiN	374	377	0.4	0.4	10
	391	391	1.2	1	8
AISI 316/7MoSS - 12 % TiN	302	494	10.0	4	60
	282	512	11.0	N/A	57
	287	573	22	12	
AISI 316/7MoSS - 30 % TiN	296	358	3.5	0.4	8
	300	362	4.0	N/A	8
	280	281	0.8	0.8	
Duplex 2205/7MoSS - 12 % TiN	469	471	2.5	2	34
	484	631	11.5	16	38
	476	607	14.0	14	
Duplex 2205/7MoSS -30 % TiN	278	278	1.0	N/A	8
	250	250	0.5	0.8	8
	155	155	0.3	0.2	
7MoSS/7MoSS - 12 % TiN	474	474	2.0	N/A	28
	487	508	3.0	3	32
	482	490	1.3	2	
7MoSS/7MoSS - 30 % TiN	385	386	2.5	2	8
	343	343	1.0	N/A	8
	379	379	0.65	0.8	

¹ N/A = not available

Figure 3. The tensile strength of the compound structures.

Figure 4. The average impact energy of the compound structures.

FRACTURE SURFACES

The fracture surfaces of the specimens were quite similar as the fracture propagated in all cases through the composite part of the compound. As an example the appearance of the fracture surface that of the AISI 316/7MoSS-30vol.%TiN tensile specimen is shown in Fig. 5 (a). A cross section of the same fracture surface is shown in Fig. 5 (b). The fracture was brittle straight through the TiN particulates and ductile through the matrix 7MoSS alloy. The fracture propagated mainly through the TiN particulates and usually in the areas where the TiN particulates were close to each other. These observations show that the bonding between the particulates and the matrix alloy is adequate for the cracking to propagate through them. Secondary fractures were frequent in the TiN particulates (Figs 5 (b) and 5 (c)) indicating that the TiN particulates were brittle.

The brittleness of the ceramic particulates obviously deteriorates the mechanical properties of the present composites. This is probably enhanced further by the sharp corners of the particulates acting as internal stress concentrators. It is probable that spherical shape of the TiN particulates would improve the properties of the composites.

Figure 5. The fracture of the AISI 316/7MoSS-30vol.%TiN tensile specimen. (a) The fracture surface, (b) a cross section of it and (c) a TiN particulate with secondary fractures.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this work show that the manufacturing of full dense TiN particulate reinforced stainless steel composite compounds can successfully be carried out by HIP techniques. However, careful filling of capsules is necessary especially at high TiN contents to prevent agglomeration of TiN at the interface between the bonded materials when an intermediate plate is used.

The addition of 12 or 30 vol.% of TiN particulates decreases the tensile strength and impact toughness of the 7MoSS matrix alloy. These values are also below those of Duplex 2205 and AISI 316.

The bonding between the composite alloys and the stainless steels is good and the compound specimens fracture through the composite part. A slight decrease in the tensile properties and a slight increase in impact strength were found as compared to bulk composites.

In the composite the fracture propagates mainly through TiN particulates indicating that the bonding between the particulates and the 7MoSS matrix alloy is strong and the TiN particulates are brittle.

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